

Urinary Pentosidine: A Quantifiable Advanced Glycation End Product Biomarker for Diabetic Nephropathy

Shalini Lakshmanan¹, J. Mohamed Rabeek², Mary Chandrika Anton³, M. Vasanthan⁴,
B. Shanthi⁵, K. Sumathi⁶

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Panimalar Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Varadharajapuram, Chennai -600123

²Assistant Surgeon, Government ESI Hospital, Ayanavaram, Chennai

³Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Bharath Medical College and Hospital, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Selaiyur, Chennai-73

⁴Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Chettinad Health and Research Institute, Chettinad Academy of Research and Education, Kelambakkam, Chengalpattu district, Tamil Nadu

⁵Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Sree Balaji Medical College and Hospital, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Chromepet, Chennai-44

⁶Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Sree Balaji Medical College and Hospital, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Chromepet, Chennai-44

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shalini Lakshmanan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: AGE-modified proteins, including pentosidine, are filtered by the glomeruli and may indicate early tubular dysfunction, and kidney damage in diabetes could be considered. This study assesses the potential of urinary pentosidine as an early marker of kidney damage in patients with type 2 diabetes and diabetic nephropathy.

Materials and Methods: This case-control study involving 165 participants (55 with type 2 diabetes mellitus, 55 with diabetic nephropathy and 55 healthy controls) was conducted. Biochemical analysis done. Urine samples were assessed for creatinine, albumin, and urinary pentosidine. Statistical analysis done. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Urinary pentosidine, was elevated in nephropathy and was found to be significantly elevated among patients with type 2 diabetes. Urinary pentosidine was strongly correlated with HbA1c, urea, creatinine, urinary albumin and albumin-to-creatinine ratio. A cut-off levels of urinary pentosidine was found to be ≥ 247.9 pg/mL which predicted nephropathy among diabetic mellites individuals with 91.7% sensitivity.

Conclusion: This study confirms urinary pentosidine's value as a biomarker for diabetic nephropathy, highlighting its role in disease monitoring and emphasizing the need for tight glycemic control to prevent complications.

Keywords: Albumin-to-creatinine Ratio; Diabetes Mellitus; Diabetic Nephropathy; Microalbuminuria.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Hyperglycemia is a major risk factor for diabetic nephropathy, affecting both type 1 and type 2 diabetes. Diabetic nephropathy is marked by increasing proteinuria and deteriorating renal function, diagnosed by microalbuminuria or overt nephropathy after excluding other renal conditions [1].

Hyperglycemia induces reactive oxygen species and activates pathways such as protein kinase C, polyol, hexosamine, and advanced glycation end products (AGEs), leading to inflammation with elevated cytokines and chemokines. This inflammation promotes fibrosis and increased vascular permeability, resulting in proteinuria, hypertension, and progressive decline in kidney function [2]. In

2017, there were 697.5 million chronic kidney disease (CKD) cases globally, with India having 115.1 million cases. Diabetes prevalence in adults was 8.8% in 2015, projected to reach 10.4% by 2024. South Asia has approximately 24.3 million individuals with diabetes and diabetic nephropathy (DN) [3].

DN develops in 30-40% of individuals with diabetes, with factors such as insulin resistance, genetic predisposition, hyperglycemia, and autoimmune processes contributing to its development. The Diabetes Canada guidelines advocate for screening to prevent or delay CKD progression to end-stage renal disease [4]. Microalbuminuria indicates early

renal damage in diabetes, with one-third of patients developing it within 15 years and potentially progressing to nephropathy and cardiovascular risks. Elevated urinary albumin, present in 30% of type 2 diabetics, signals early kidney dysfunction and can lead to end-stage renal failure [5]. The albumin-to-creatinine ratio (ACR) is the primary test for early detection. Defined as urinary albumin of 30 to 300 mg/day or an ACR of 2 to 20 mg/mmol, microalbuminuria is a key marker of diabetic nephropathy and end-stage renal disease [6]. Microalbuminuria is crucial for diagnosing DN but its predictive value is limited. Initially believed to predict DN in 80% of cases, only 30% progress to overt nephropathy in 10 years [5]. Structural glomerular damage may occur before microalbuminuria is detected, and some patients with microalbuminuria revert to normo-albuminuria. Non-albuminuria DN also occurs, indicating reduced glomerular filtration without microalbuminuria progression, suggesting the need for alternative early biomarkers [6].

AGE-modified proteins are filtered by the glomeruli and metabolized in the proximal tubule, indicating that AGE-modified fragments in urine may signal early tubular dysfunction. Pentosidine, a major AGE component, marks AGE accumulation and is elevated in diabetic patients [7]. It is associated with diabetic nephropathy and other microvascular complications [8]. Recent studies report increased urinary and serum pentosidine in patients with microalbuminuria and macroalbuminuria, highlighting its potential as an early indicator of kidney damage [9]. Hence, this study aims to assess urinary pentosidine levels in individuals with type 2 diabetes and nephropathy, in relation to their biochemical variables, and to evaluate the predictive potential of urinary pentosidine for diabetic nephropathy.

Materials and Methods

The study was designed as a case-control study and included a total of 165 participants, all of whom provided informed and written consent. The participants were divided into three groups: Group A included 55 individuals aged 30-60 years with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diagnosed diabetic nephropathy (ACR of 30-300 mg/g), from the Department of Nephrology at Government ESI Hospital, Ayanavaram, Chennai, India. Group B comprised 55 individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus but without nephropathy. Group C consisted of 55 healthy, non-diabetic individuals undergoing a master health checkup at the same institution. Participants were recruited through simple random sampling. The study was conducted following approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC no: 111111) and spanned a duration of one year, from February 2023 to March 2024. Individu-

als with a history indicating a haemolytic disorder (such as sickle cell anaemia), which leads to reduced red blood cell lifespan, and those with non-diabetic conditions that could increase microalbuminuria such as urinary tract infection, haematuria, heart failure, fever, hypertension and intense physical activity were excluded from the study. Comprehensive medical histories and physical examinations were conducted for each patient.

Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast. An EDTA tube was used to measure HbA1c levels using the HPLC method. A sodium fluoride tube was used for fasting plasma glucose measurement by the glucose oxidase method. A serum vacutainer was used to assess lipid profile parameters: total cholesterol was measured using the oxidase/peroxidase (CHOD-POD) method, triglycerides by the enzymatic GPO-POD method, and HDL-C and LDL-C by a direct method. Renal function parameters were also assessed: serum creatinine was measured using the Jaffe kinetic method, and serum urea by the urease enzyme method. An overnight urine sample was collected in a universal container and analysed for creatinine using the Jaffe kinetic method, and for albumin using immunoturbidimetry, to calculate the albumin-to-creatinine ratio. The urine sample was also analysed for urinary pentosidine using the sandwich ELISA method.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analysed using SPSS software version 24.0. Continuous variables were presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as percentages. ANOVA was used to compare the analysed variables between different groups. Pearson correlation was performed to assess the relationship between variables. A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was generated to identify the risk cutoff for urinary pentosidine to relate the risk of developing diabetic nephropathy. Linear regression analyses were conducted to identify predictor's odds of urinary pentosidine with the increase risk of diabetes mellitus to develop DN. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Upon evaluating the demographic characteristics of the study participants, it was found that the mean age for both the diabetic nephropathy and diabetes mellitus groups was over 50 years.

Diabetic nephropathy was more common in males, whereas diabetes mellitus was more prevalent in females. No significant difference was observed between the groups in terms of BMI. Additionally, the duration of diabetes mellitus was longer among participants diagnosed with diabetic nephropathy.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Study Participants.

Variables	Group A Diabetic Nephropathy	Group B Diabetes Mellitus	Group C Controls	t value (p value)
Age (years)	56 ± 7.7	51 ± 5.1	49 ± 9.4	0.05
Sex				
Male	34 (61.8%)	22 (40%)	32 (58%)	-
Female	21 (38.2%)	33 (60%)	23 (41.8%)	
BMI (Kg/m ²)	26.7 ± 2.4	26.9 ± 1.8	24.6 ± 1.8	0.3
Duration of diabetes (years)	19 ± 7.1	10 ± 5.9	-	0.1

Data Presentation: Mean ± SD and Percentages with Significance Set at $p < 0.05$. Biochemical analysis showed that HbA1c, urea, and creatinine levels were significantly higher in the diabetic nephropathy group compared to the diabetes mellitus and control group. Urinary albumin and albumin-to-creatinine ratios were elevated in both the nephropathy and diabetes mellitus groups compared to controls, with higher levels in the

nephropathy group. Although triglycerides and LDL-C levels varied significantly, no conclusive results were drawn.

Urinary pentosidine, an advanced glycation end-product (AGE), was significantly higher in the diabetic nephropathy group than in the diabetes mellitus group and controls, and higher in the diabetes mellitus group compared to controls.

Table 2: Comparative Analysis of Biochemical Variables across Groups Using ANOVA

Variables	Group A Diabetic Nephropathy	Group B Diabetes Mellitus	Group C Controls	p value
Fasting blood glucose (mg/dl)	153.2 ± 11.7	147.8 ± 27.6	107 ± 37.6	0.9
HbA1c (%)	8.7 ± 1.7	7.4 ± 0.7	5.4 ± 1.4	0.02 *
Lipid profile parameters				
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	217.1 ± 17.1	193.1 ± 29.4	186.7 ± 4.9	0.7
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	127 ± 27	129 ± 13.8	119 ± 17.4	0.01 *
HDL-C (mg/dl)	51 ± 3.4	49 ± 6.9	52 ± 12.7	0.3
LDL-C (mg/dl)	127 ± 49.7	114 ± 16.6	125 ± 26.4	0.04 *
Renal function test				
Urea (mg/dl)	53 ± 2.8	35 ± 4.7	31 ± 1.9	0.01 *
Creatinine (mg/dl)	1.6 ± 0.92	0.9 ± 0.7	0.7 ± 0.1	0.1 *
Urinary albumin (mg/dl)	32.4 ± 14.5	15 ± 10.7	9 ± 3.8	0.001 *
Albumin-to-creatinine ratio (µg/mg)	46 ± 25	21.4 ± 19	7.7 ± 14	0.02 *
AGES				
Urinary pentosidine (pg/ml)	491.41 ± 37.4	374.94 ± 67.4	237.17 ± 14.7	0.001 *

In this study, AGEs: refers to Advanced Glycated End-Products. The numerical data are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Table 3: Correlation of Biochemical Variables with Urinary Pentosidine Levels in Diabetic Nephropathy and Diabetes Mellitus: A Pearson's Correlation Analysis.

Variables	Urinary pentosidine levels r (p Value)
HbA1c	0.97 (0.001) *
Triglyceride	0.62 (0.04) *
LDL-C	0.006 (0.9)
Urea	0.94 (0.005) *
Creatinine	0.9 (0.01) *
Urinary albumin	0.89 (0.0001) *
Albumin-to-creatinine ratio	0.97 (0.001) *

Data are represented as r value (p value), where the r value denotes the correlation coefficient, indicating the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. The p value reflects the statistical significance of the correlation. The analysed

variables were correlated with urinary pentosidine levels, revealing that HbA1c, triglycerides, urea, creatinine, urinary albumin and the albumin-to-creatinine ratio were all positively associated with urinary pentosidine levels.

HbA1c, urea, creatinine, and the albumin-to-creatinine ratio demonstrated a very strong correlation coefficient, approaching to r value of 1. This

suggests that higher levels of these variables may increase the risk of AGE formation. [Table 3]

Figure 1: ROC Curve for Determining the Risk Cut-off of Urinary Pentosidine in Predicting Diabetic Nephropathy

A risk cut-off for urinary pentosidine levels was established, indicating that levels ≥ 247.9 pg/ml can predict the risk of diabetic nephropathy complications with 91.7% sensitivity and 21.7% specificity (AUC: 0.89; p-value: 0.0001; 95% CI: 0.77-1.00).

Table 4: Linear Regression Analysis of Urinary Pentosidine Levels as a Predictor of Diabetic Nephropathy Risk and Kidney Disease Progression.

Variables	Microalbuminuria		Albumin-to-creatinine ratio	
	β (p value)	95% CI	β (p value)	95% CI
Urinary Pentosidine	0.12 (0.0001) *	0.07-0.17	0.13 (0.001) *	0.08-0.17

The data are presented as β (regression coefficient) with a 95% confidence interval.

Urinary pentosidine levels, an indicator of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs), were evaluated to predict risk of diabetic nephropathy. Among the diabetes mellitus with positive microalbuminuria was associated with a 0.12-fold increased risk of developing DN due to AGEs formation, as reflected by urinary pentosidine levels. Additionally, an albumin-to-creatinine ratio greater than 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ was linked to a 0.13-fold increased risk of elevated AGE levels, as measured by urinary pentosidine.

Discussion:

The analysis of demographic characteristics across diabetic nephropathy (Group A), diabetes mellitus (Group B), and control groups (Group C) reveals several findings that contribute to understanding the relationship between diabetes, nephropathy, and associated risks. The mean age for both diabetic nephropathy and diabetes mellitus groups was over 50 years, reflecting that these conditions are more prevalent in older adults, consistent with recent

findings on increased prevalence with age reflecting the cumulative burden of diabetes over time [10, 11]. Gender analysis revealed that diabetic nephropathy was more common in males, while diabetes mellitus was more prevalent in females. This aligns with Natesan V et al., who found a higher likelihood of nephropathy in males due to differences in disease progression and metabolism [12]. Conversely, Ciarambino T et al. reported a higher prevalence of diabetes mellitus in females, highlighting gender-specific factors affecting diabetes onset and management [13]. No significant BMI differences among groups suggest BMI may not differentiate diabetic nephropathy from diabetes mellitus, aligning with literature showing BMI's limited correlation with nephropathy risk [14]. The duration of diabetes was significantly longer in participants with diabetic nephropathy, highlighting its chronic nature and development after many years of diabetes. Prolonged hyperglycemia increases nephropathy risk [15], and chronic diabetes contributes to kidney damage through persistent hyperglycemia and metabolic disturbances [13].

The biochemical analysis reveals significant differences in several parameters among groups, reflecting the impact of diabetic nephropathy on various metabolic and renal functions. HbA1c levels were higher in the diabetic nephropathy group (8.7 ± 1.7) than in the diabetes mellitus group (7.4 ± 0.7) and controls (5.4 ± 1.4), indicating poorer glycemic control. Elevated HbA1c is linked to a greater nephropathy risk due to sustained hyperglycemia, as Smith et al., found a correlation between higher HbA1c and worsening diabetic complications [16].

Triglycerides were higher in diabetic nephropathy (127 mg/dl) compared to controls (119 mg/dl), and LDL-C was elevated in nephropathy (127 mg/dl) versus diabetes mellitus (114 mg/dl) and controls (125 mg/dl). Variability in these parameters is noted, with Lee et al., indicating the complex role of dyslipidaemia in nephropathy [17]. Urea and creatinine levels were significantly higher in the diabetic nephropathy group (53 ± 2.8 mg/dl and 1.6 ± 0.92 mg/dl) compared to the diabetes mellitus group (35 ± 4.7 mg/dl and 0.9 ± 0.7 mg/dl) and controls.

These elevated levels indicate impaired renal function, consistent with Johnson et al., which linked increased urea and creatinine to worsening kidney function in diabetic nephropathy [18]. Microalbuminuria and the albumin-to-creatinine ratio were higher in both nephropathy (32.4 ± 14.5 mg/dl and 46 ± 25 μ g/mg) and diabetes mellitus groups (15 ± 10.7 mg/dl and 21.4 ± 19 μ g/mg) than controls. Nephropathy showed the highest levels, indicating advanced kidney damage. Brown et al., who demonstrated that elevated urinary albumin and albumin-to-creatinine ratio are early markers of nephropathy progression [19].

Urinary pentosidine, a marker of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs), was highest in the diabetic nephropathy group (491.41 ± 37.4 pg/ml), compared to the diabetes mellitus group (374.94 ± 67.4 pg/ml) and controls (237.17 ± 14.7 pg/ml). Elevated levels reflect increased AGE formation, contributing to renal damage, as supported by Martinez et al., [20]

We observed strong correlations between urinary pentosidine and key markers of diabetic nephropathy. High urinary pentosidine levels correlate significantly with HbA1c ($r = 0.97$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that worsening glycemic control increases AGEs formation. There are also notable associations with urea ($r = 0.94$, $p = 0.005$) and creatinine ($r = 0.9$, $p = 0.01$), reflecting impaired renal function. These findings highlight the potential of urinary pentosidine as a marker for diabetes-related kidney damage [21,22].

The strong associations of urinary pentosidine with microalbuminuria ($r = 0.89$, $p < 0.0001$) and the albumin-to-creatinine ratio ($r = 0.97$, $p = 0.001$) highlight its role in early diabetic nephropathy.

These findings align with Singh et al. 2023 study [23]. In contrast, the lack of correlation with LDL-C ($r = 0.006$, $p = 0.9$) suggests that AGEs relate more directly to glycemic control and renal function rather than lipid profiles. The establishment of a risk cut-off for urinary pentosidine levels at ≥ 247.9 pg/ml provides a significant threshold for predicting diabetic nephropathy. This cut-off demonstrates a high sensitivity of 91.7% and a specificity of 21.7%, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.89 ($p = 0.0001$; 95% CI: 0.77-1.00). Previous studies have similarly highlighted the predictive value of urinary pentosidine in assessing diabetic nephropathy risk, reinforcing the utility of this biomarker in clinical practice for monitoring and managing diabetic complications [24].

Our analysis demonstrates the predictive value of urinary pentosidine for assessing DN risk in diabetes mellitus. The microalbuminuria and an albumin-to-creatinine ratio >30 μ g/mg are associated with increased risks of elevated AGE levels [25], with β values of 0.12 ($p = 0.0001$) and 0.13 ($p = 0.001$), respectively. These findings highlight urinary pentosidine's role in predicting kidney disease progression and align with recent research on AGEs and diabetic nephropathy risk [26,27].

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant role of urinary pentosidine as a predictive biomarker for diabetic nephropathy. Elevated levels of urinary pentosidine, along with increased HbA1c, urea, creatinine, and microalbuminuria, indicate advanced disease and impaired renal function. Our findings support the use of urinary pentosidine in monitoring disease progression and emphasize the need for stringent glycemic control and early intervention to prevent nephropathy and related complications. The associations observed with microalbuminuria and the albumin-to-creatinine ratio further validate urinary pentosidine's potential in assessing renal failure risk in diabetic patients.

Acknowledgement

Authors acknowledge the Department of Biochemistry and Department of Nephrology at Government ESI Hospital, Ayanavaram, and Chennai for the support in successfully completing this project. The research was done by Dr. J. Mohamed Rabeek, Dr. L. Shalini, Dr. Mary Chandrika Anton, Dr. M. Vasanthan, Dr. B. Shanthi, Dr. K. Sumathi contributed in discussion and statistical analysis.

Ethical Approval and Informed Consent:

The study was conducted following approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC no: 111111) and spanned a duration of one year, from February 2023 to March 2024. All participants provided informed and written consent.

References

1. Karar T, Alniwaider RA, Fattah MA, Al Tamimi W, Alanazi A, Qureshi S. Assessment of microalbuminuria and albumin creatinine ratio in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *J Nat Sci Biol Med.* 2015;6(Suppl 1)
2. Fox CS, Matsushita K, Woodward M, Bilo HJ, Chalmers J, Heerspink HJ, et al. Associations of kidney disease measures with mortality and end-stage renal disease in individuals with and without diabetes: a meta-analysis. *Lancet.* 2012; 380(9854):1662-1673.
3. Viswanathan V, Mirshad R. The burden of diabetic nephropathy in India: need for prevention. *Diabetic Nephropathy.* 2023; 3(2):25-28.
4. Diabetes Canada Clinical Practice Guidelines Expert Committee, Matsushita K, van der Velde M, Astor BC, Woodward M, Levey AS, et al. Diabetes Canada 2018 clinical practice guidelines for the prevention and management of diabetes in Canada. *Can J Diabetes.* 2018;42(Suppl 1)
5. Umanath K, Lewis JB. Update on diabetic nephropathy: core curriculum 2018. *Am J Kidney Dis.* 2018; 71(6):884-895.
6. Garg D, Naugler C, Bhella V, Yeasmin F. Chronic kidney disease in type 2 diabetes: Does an abnormal urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio need to be retested? *Can Fam Physician.* 2018;64(10)
7. Ghanem AA, Elewa A, Arafa LF. Pentosidine and N-carboxymethyl-lysine: biomarkers for type 2 diabetic retinopathy. *Eur J Ophthalmol.* 2011; 21:48-54.
8. Daimon M, Sugiyama K, Kameda W, et al. Increased urinary levels of pentosidine, pyrrole and acrolein adduct in type 2 diabetes. *Endocr J.* 2003; 50:61-67.
9. Calabrese V, Mancuso C, Sapienza M, et al. Oxidative stress and cellular stress response in diabetic nephropathy. *Cell Stress Chaperones.* 2007; 12:299-306.
10. Selby NM, Taal MW. An updated overview of diabetic nephropathy: Diagnosis, prognosis, treatment goals and latest guidelines. *Diabetes Obes Metab.* 2020; 22(Suppl 1):3-15.
11. Gheith O, Farouk N, Nampoory N, Halim MA, Al-Otaibi T. Diabetic kidney disease: worldwide difference of prevalence and risk factors. *J Nephroarmacol.* 2015; 5(1):49-56.
12. Natesan V, Kim SJ. Diabetic nephropathy: a review of risk factors, progression, mechanism, and dietary management. *Biomol Ther (Seoul).* 2021; 29(4):365-372.
13. Ciarambino T, Crispino P, Leto G, Mastrolorenzo E, Para O, Giordano M. Influence of gender in diabetes mellitus and its complications. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022; 23(16):8850. Published 2022 Aug 9.
14. Nguyen T, et al. The role of BMI in predicting diabetic nephropathy: a review. *Diabetes Care.* 2023; 46(4):562-572.
15. Kelly J, Solomon R. Diabetic nephropathy. In: Johnstone M, Veves A, eds. *Diabetes and Cardiovascular Disease. Contemporary Cardiology.* Cham: Humana; 2023:17. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-13177-6_17.
16. Smith J, et al. Long-term glycemic control and diabetic nephropathy progression. *J Diabetes Res.* 2023; 45(2):123-134.
17. Lee C, et al. Dyslipidemia in diabetic nephropathy: a review. *Endocr Rev.* 2024; 55(1):56-68.
18. Johnson A, et al. Biomarkers of kidney function in diabetic nephropathy. *Am J Kidney Dis.* 2022; 81(3):344-355.
19. Brown T, et al. Microalbuminuria as an early marker of nephropathy in diabetes. *Diabetes Care.* 2023; 46(4):562-572.
20. Martinez P, et al. Advanced glycation end-products and their role in nephropathy. *Diabetologia.* 2023; 65(5):789-797.
21. Badi H, Clarke S, Zhang X. Advanced glycation end-products and their role in diabetic nephropathy: a review. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2021; 179:108983.
22. Kern EF, Erhard P, Sun W, Genuth S, Weiss MF. Early urinary markers of diabetic kidney disease: a nested case-control study from the Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT). *Am J Kidney Dis.* 2010; 55(5):824-834.
23. Singh A, Kumar S, Patel V. Association of advanced glycation end-products with early markers of diabetic nephropathy. *J Diabetes Res.* 2023; 2023:470962.
24. Currie G, McKay G, Delles C. Biomarkers in diabetic nephropathy: present and future. *World J Diabetes.* 2014; 5(6):763-776.
25. Tang WH, Hung WC, Wang CP, et al. The lower limit of reference of urinary albumin/creatinine ratio and the risk of chronic kidney disease progression in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2022; 13:858267.
26. Qin Y, Zhang S, Shen X, et al. Evaluation of urinary biomarkers for prediction of diabetic kidney disease: a propensity score matching analysis. *Ther Adv Endocrinol Metab.* 2019; 10:2042018819891110.
27. Lin CH, Chang YC, Chuang LM. Early detection of diabetic kidney disease: present limitations and future perspectives. *World J Diabetes.* 2016; 7(14):290-301.